

Impact Factor: 5.19

ISSN: 2181-0664

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 5, Issue 2

2024

ISSN 2181-0664

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0664

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 2

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 2

ТОШКЕНТ-2024

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

№2 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2024-2>

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ISSN: 2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

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FEATURES OF THE COURSE, MORPHO-FUNCTIONAL AND CLINICAL-INSTRUMENTAL INDICATORS OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA WITH MYOCARDITIS IN CHILDREN

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11396962>

ABSTRACT

Myocarditis is an inflammatory lesion of the myocardium of infectious, toxic-infectious, infectious-allergic, autoimmune, or toxic etiology (3,4). Despite the research, the problem of myocarditis in children remains unresolved, which is associated with a variety of etiological factors and clinical, laboratory and instrumental manifestations of the disease. The search for differential diagnostic criteria and additional methods of pathogenetic therapy for the disease continues. In the study, in the majority of children with pneumonia, the plasma component of hemostasis was activated, a shortening of clotting time, hyperfibrinogenemia, a decrease in platelets, prothrombin index, and fibrinogen occurred; in a minority (19.64%) of children with pneumonia, the fibrinolytic activity of the blood increased. The authors recommend correcting the detection of changes with hemostabilizing drugs. The paper presents the results of anamnestic, clinical, generally accepted laboratory and unique examination methods in 80 children with community-acquired pneumonia aged 1 to 6 years, of which 40 patients with concomitant myocarditis who were hospitalized in the departments of the II Emergency Pediatrics and Pediatric Intensive Care Unit of Samarkand branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care in the period from 2020 to 2022.

Keywords: pneumonia, myocarditis, children, ExoKG, analysis, laboratory, fibrinolysis, prothrombin, hemostasis, blood.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕЧЕНИЯ, МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И КЛИНИКО-ИНСТРУМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ВНЕБОЛЬНИЧНОЙ ПНЕВМОНИИ С МИОКАРДИТОМ У ДЕТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Миокардит — воспалительное поражение миокарда инфекционной, токсико-инфекционной, инфекционно-аллергической, аутоиммунной или токсической этиологии (3,4). Несмотря на исследования, проблема миокардита у детей до сих пор остается нерешенной, что связано с разнообразием этиологических факторов, клинических, лабораторных и инструментальных проявлений заболевания. Продолжается поиск дифференциально-диагностических критериев и дополнительных методов патогенетической терапии заболевания. В ходе исследования у большинства детей с пневмонией активировался плазменный компонент гемостаза, наблюдалось укорочение времени свертывания крови, гиперфибриногенемия, снижение тромбоцитов, протромбинового индекса и фибриногена; у меньшинства (19,64%) детей с пневмонией повышалась фибринолитическая активность крови. Авторы рекомендуют корректировать обнаружение изменений гемостабилизирующими препаратами. В работе представлены результаты анамнестических, клинических, общепринятых лабораторных и специальных методов обследования 80 детей с внебольничной пневмонией в возрасте от 1 до 6 лет, из них 40 больных с сопутствующим миокардитом, госпитализированных в отделения II скорой педиатрической помощи и детского отделения интенсивной терапии Самаркандского филиала Республиканского научного центра скорой медицинской помощи в период с 2020 по 2022 год.

Ключевые слова: пневмония, миокардит, дети, ЭхоКГ, анализ, лаборатория, фибринолиз, протромбин, гемостаз, кровь.

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**BOLALARDA MIOKARDIT BILAN SHIFOXONADAN TASHQARI PNEVMONIYANING
KECHISH, MORFO-FUNKSIONAL VA KLINIK-INSTRUMENTAL
KO'RSATKICHLARINING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI**

ANNOTATSIYA

Miokardit - miokardning yuqumli, toksik-infektsion, yuqumli-allergik, autoimmun yoki toksik etiologiyali yallig'lanishli zararlanish (3,4). Tadqiqotlarga qaramay, bolalarda miokardit muammosi haligacha hal etilmagan bo'lib, bu turli xil etiologik omillar, kasallikning klinik, laboratoriya va instrumental ko'rinishlari bilan bog'liq. Kasallik uchun differentsial diagnostika mezonlari va patogenetik terapiyaning qo'shimcha usullarini izlash davom etmoqda. Tadqiqot davomida pnevmoniya bilan og'rigan bolalarning ko'pchiligida gemostazning plazma komponenti faollashdi, qon ivish vaqtining qisqarishi, giperfibrinogenemiya, trombositlar, protrombin indeksi va fibrinogenning pasayishi kuzatildi; pnevmoniya bilan og'rigan bolalarning ozchiligida (19,64%) qonning fibrinolitik faolligi oshdi. Bir qator mualliflar gemostabilizatsiya qiluvchi dorilar bilan o'zgarishlarni aniqlashni tuzatishni tavsiya qiladilar. Maqolada Respublika shoshilinch tibbiy yordam ilmiy markazi Samarqand filiali bolalar reanimatsiyasi bo'limi, I-II bolalar bo'limlarida 2020-2022-yillarda 1 yoshdan 6 yoshgacha bo'lgan 80 nafar shifoxonadan tashqari pnevmoniya bilan og'rigan, ulardan 40 nafari miokardit bilan kasallangan bolalarning anamnestik, klinik, laborator va maxsus tekshirish usullari natijalari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: pnevmoniya, miokardit, bolalar, ExoKG, tahlil, laboratoriya, fibrinoliz, protrombin, gemostaz, qon.

Relevance. Currently, optimization of methods for diagnosing and treating pneumonia in children is a priority worldwide (1,3).

The pulse oximetry method, which measures arterial blood oxygen saturation, must be used in all patients with CAP for an objective assessment of the severity of the disease and the scope of therapeutic measures (5).

Myocarditis is an inflammatory lesion of the myocardium of infectious, toxic-infectious, infectious-allergic, autoimmune or toxic etiology (3,4). Despite the research, the problem of myocarditis in children remains unresolved, which is associated with a variety of etiological factors, clinical, laboratory and instrumental manifestations of the disease. The search for differential diagnostic criteria and additional methods of pathogenetic therapy for the disease continues. In the study, in the majority of children with pneumonia, the plasma component of hemostasis was activated, a shortening of clotting time, hyperfibrinogenemia, a decrease in platelets, prothrombin index, and fibrinogen occurred; in a minority (19.64%) of children with pneumonia, the fibrinolytic activity of the blood increased. The authors recommend correcting the detection of changes with hemostabilizing drugs (1.6).

In young children with severe, complicated pneumonia and bronchitis, compensatory hypercoagulation, subcompensatory and decompensatory hypercoagulation are determined hypercoagulation, a transition from hypercoagulation to hypocoagulation, intravascular coagulation, increased amount of fibrinogen, thrombinemia, decreased fibrinolysis (3,5,7).

The purpose of the study - is to study the characteristics of clinical and instrumental indicators of community-acquired pneumonia with myocarditis in children.

Materials and methods of research. The paper presents the results of anamnestic, clinical, generally accepted laboratory and special examination methods in 80 children with community-acquired pneumonia aged 1 to 6 years, of which 40 patients with concomitant myocarditis who were hospitalized in the departments of the II Emergency Pediatrics and Pediatric Intensive Care Unit of Samarkand branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care in the period from 2020 to 2021.

Patients in the 1st stage of the study were divided into 3 groups:

Group I included 40 children with community-acquired pneumonia without myocarditis.

II included 40 patients with mild and moderate course of community-acquired pneumonia due to myocarditis.

All patients underwent generally accepted clinical, laboratory and instrumental examinations and special research methods.

Results of the study and their discussions.

The examination of patients with CAP and ILM showed that the clinical symptoms mainly correspond to the main manifestations of the disease but also to the frequent involvement of other vital organs and systems in the pathological process.

The contingency analysis carried out to determine the significance of clinical symptoms in patients revealed several indicators that had varying degrees of reliability, characterizing the features of the course of CAP compared with ILM.

Thus, a moderately severe condition was more often observed with VP ($\chi^2 - 0.46, P = 0.499$), a severe condition with ILM ($\chi^2 - 52.38, P = 0.000$), which reflects the combination of pathologies. Fatigue ($\chi^2 - 31.65, P=0.0001$), decreased appetite ($\chi^2 - 42.08, P=0.000$) and acrocyanosis are significantly more common in ILM ($\chi^2 - 12.47, P=0.0000$) are manifestation of myocarditis.

Respiratory failure of the 1st degree, which occurred more often in patients of the VP group ($\chi^2 - 0.00, P = 1.0$), while in the combined course of pneumonia and myocarditis, when the load on the gas exchange processes of the lungs increases, and respiratory failure of the 3rd degree was significantly more common with ILM ($\chi^2 - 6.49, P=0.011$).

Thus, the results of the study show that the frequency of detection of clinical manifestations in children with ILM in comparison with CAP is determined by fatigue in 65.0% and 5.0% of cases, loss of appetite in 87.5% and 15.0%, acrocyanosis in 32.5% and 2.5%, tachycardia in 85.0% and 7.5%, arrhythmias in 27.5% and 2.5%, an increase in the boundaries of the heart in 60.0% and 2.5%, systolic murmur in 42.5% and 5.0% of cases, respectively.

Analysis of the manifestations of cardiac symptoms, as the most informative signs of the course of ILM, showed that the leading significant diagnostic criteria of the disease are tachycardia ($\chi^2 - 48.32$, $P = 0.000$), arrhythmias ($\chi^2 - 9.8$, $P = 0.002$), enlarged heart boundaries ($\chi^2 - 15.76$, $P=0.0001$) and systolic murmur ($\chi^2 - 15.53$, $P=0.000$).

The diagnostic significance of other signs was relatively low and unreliable.

Analysis of the dynamics of elimination of the main clinical manifestations in patients with CAP showed that almost all the most important clinical symptoms of the disease normalized significantly faster ($P < 0.001$). Thus, an improvement in the general condition was observed on 4.3 ± 0.2 days, normalization of the temperature reaction on 3.9 ± 0.2 , elimination of pathological auscultation data in the lungs by 6.7 ± 0.3 , disappearance of DN by 4.9 ± 0.2 , tachycardia by 3.7 ± 0.3 days, in comparison with patients with an uncomplicated course ILM (5.9 ± 0.2 ; 6.1 ± 0.3 , 8.2 ± 0.3 , 7.5 ± 0.3 , 8.5 ± 0.3 , respectively, group B, including length of hospital stay - 9.4 ± 0.5 and 10.9 ± 0.4 bed days, respectively ($P < 0.05$).

The lengthening of the period of normalization of the symptoms of the disease in the uncomplicated course of ILM is quite understandable and natural, so with the combined course of pneumonia and myocarditis in children, taking into account the similar pathogenetic mechanism of disturbances in metabolic, hemostatic processes that occur when the respiratory and cardiovascular systems are damaged, the pathological processes of diseases intensify.

Thus, in patients with ILM, there is a significant slowdown in the time of normalization of the clinical symptoms of the disease in comparison with CAP, which is associated with the synergistic effect of pneumonia and myocarditis on pathological processes, including metabolic and hemostatic, during the development of the disease.

Features of clinical symptoms in children with community-acquired pneumonia with myocarditis can be diagnostic criteria for the course of the disease; our planned development of treatment methods will be covered in more detail in subsequent chapters of the work.

Analysis of echocardiography studies in patients with CAP showed (Table 3.2) that with the development of the disease, ESR indicators significantly expanded by 17.8%, ESR increased by 44.7% and EDV increased by 15.2% compared to normative values ($P < 0.05$, $P < 0.02$, $P < 0.001$). At that time, an increase in the size of the CDR by 8.3% (4.03 ± 0.17 cm), manifested by an increase in SV by 9.5% and EF by 8.7%, compared with the data of children in the control group, there was no significant difference ($P > 0.1$, $P > 0.2$).

Thus, one of the significant criteria for hemodynamic violations in children with VP is an increase in TFR, expansion CSR and EDV, which must be used to assess CVS in patients.

Thus, as myocarditis develops in pneumonia in children, significant changes occur in echocardiographic parameters, which are the most essential instrumental criteria for assessing the state of the cardiovascular system. Echocardiography studies show that in cases of pneumonia in children and the development of myocarditis, influence on condition intracardiac hemodynamics complicates the clinical course And predetermines the development of cardiovascular complications of the disease. The identified features of echocardiography indices for ILM are an increase in ESR (3.83 ± 0.11 cm), ESR (62.68 ± 1.70 ml), ESD (4.97 ± 0.13 cm), EDV (114.82 ± 2.39 ml), SV (52.16 ± 1.09 ml) and decreased EF (45.2 ± 1.5 %).

Conclusion. Thus, echocardiography shows changes in hemodynamic parameters, indicating an increase in the load on the left side of the heart, to a greater extent in cases of complicated ILM. This is probably due to the direct and indirect toxic effects of microbial -viral endo- and exotoxins formed during the development of pneumonia and myocarditis on organs and tissues, including the myocardium. Changes in intracardiac hemodynamics in patients are caused by changes in the cardiovascular system (myocarditis) and the bronchopulmonary system (community-acquired pneumonia).

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ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 2

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 2

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